

22DIT01 ViDiT

D6 Report on how to account for errors in the surrogate models of VEs and DTs, which need to be used for computationally expensive systems (this report will use 1 VE application (FLOW) and 1 DT application (3D robotics) as examples)

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable: VSL

Due date of the deliverable: 31.10.2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 26.01.2026

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EURAMET. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

DELIVERABLE D6: Report on how to account for errors in the surrogate models of virtual experiments and digital twins

Authors (alphabetically): Asier García Berdote
Björn Hemming
Brahim Ahmed
Gertjan Kok
Jon Flores
Marcel van Dijk
Nursen Bayazit
Pablo Puerto
Sonja Schmelter

Confidentiality: Confidential until 30-04-2026

Submission date: 31-01-2026

Version: 1.0

vidit.ptb.de

Contents

Glossary and symbols 3

1. Introduction 4

2. A surrogate model for high-fidelity flow simulations 5

- 2.1. Surrogate Model Construction 5
- 2.2. Model Improvement and Criteria for Refinement 5
- 2.3. Separation of Calibration and Validation Data 6
- 2.4. Treatment of Error and Uncertainty Sources 6
- 2.5. Surrogate Model Validation 7

3. A surrogate model of a welded part 13

- 3.1. The part 13
- 3.2. Need of surrogate model 13
- 3.3. Surrogate model 15
- 3.4. Errors in the surrogate model 16

4. A surrogate model for a 3D robotic DT 19

- 4.1. Surrogate model construction 19
- 4.2. Model improvement 20
- 4.3. Separation of calibration and validation data 21
- 4.4. Treatment of Different Error Sources 22

References 24

Glossary and symbols

XXX	Description of abbreviation or symbol
VE	Virtual Experiment
DT	Digital Twin
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
LDV	Laser-Doppler-Velocimetry
GP	Gaussian Process
GPR	Gaussian Process Regression
RBF	Radial Basis Function
AR-MF	Auto-Regressive Multi-Fidelity
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
FE	Finite Element (method), computational method for predicting an object's behaviour
CAD	Computer-aided design
STL	Stereolithography file, a file type for describing the surface geometry of a three-dimensional object
CMM	Coordinate Measuring Machine
MC	Monte Carlo
$\mu(x)$	Mean function
$\sigma^2(x)$	Observation variance
S	Score function
R_c/D	Normalized curvature radius
w_{vol}	Volumetric flow rate
z/D	Normalized downstream distance at test rig
d_1/D	Normalized distance between two bends at test rig
w_{sym}	Symmetric velocity component
w_{asym}	Asymmetric velocity component
w_{norm}	Normalized axial velocity
r/R	Normalized radius of polar grid
φ	Azimuthal angle of polar grid
k_{alpha}	Conformal calibration factor

1. Introduction

Trustworthy Virtual Experiments (VEs) and Digital Twins (DTs) are key enabling technologies to achieve and realise European strategic policies devoted to sustainability and digitalisation within the complex framework of Industry 4.0 and the European Green Deal. However, in some situations it may not be practical to use a (usually computationally expensive) VE or DT directly in an end-user application. One such an application field is given by operational setups that require short computational times, such as on-line quality controls, in which a single run of the computational model should be very fast. In other applications, e.g. when evaluating the uncertainty using a Monte Carlo method and involving a VE or DT, the total of, let's say 10 000, runs of the computational model should finish within a reasonable time period.

As a replacement for computationally expensive VEs and DTs so-called surrogate models can be developed, validated and used. Surrogate models are computationally fast models, which are usually less accurate than the full models implemented in the VE/DT.

This report describes how to account for errors in the surrogate models of VEs and DTs. This will be done along the lines of three use cases which are presented in the next three chapters. These chapters cover surrogate model construction, model improvements to meet set specifications, how to separate calibration and validation data and how to treat different error sources.

The first use case, presented in Chapter 2, describes a surrogate model for high-fidelity flow simulations. The surrogate model is constructed using Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), which is able to fuse high-fidelity and low-fidelity data into a single representation.

Chapter 3 deals with a surrogate model for a welded part. Simplified parametric models are developed replacing more accurate but more computationally expensive representations of the part.

Finally, Chapter 4 present a surrogate model for a three-dimensional robotic DT. In this work, the dimensionality of the model is significantly reduced by assessing the correlations between different input parameters.

After studying these chapters, it is expected that the reader has received some useful insights and suggestions for building, validating and accounting for errors in surrogate models for VEs and DTs.

2. A surrogate model for high-fidelity flow simulations

2.1. Surrogate Model Construction

The surrogate model considered in this chapter serves as a computationally efficient representation of high-fidelity flow data. It replaces expensive numerical models, such as computational fluid dynamics (CFD), as well as experimental measurements, such as Laser-Doppler-Velocimetry (LDV), by providing a fast, differentiable and statistically interpretable approximation of the two-dimensional velocity field at various downstream positions. The surrogate model can predict the flow field downstream of a variety of different S-elbow configurations, which will be described in more detail below. The predictions of the surrogate model can then be used as input to virtual flow experiments by applying different measurement principles to obtain virtual fluid-mechanical calibration factors. The following sections are partly based on and present content from [1].

The surrogate is constructed using GPR due to its ability to fuse high-fidelity LDV and low-fidelity CFD data, its flexibility in modelling local non-linear variations and global trends, its natural incorporation of heterogeneous noise levels α , where α represents observation variance assigned to each data source, and its ability to provide both mean predictions and uncertainty estimates with very little high-fidelity data. Furthermore, a GPR model is capable of learning the relationship between input parameters (e.g. flow conditions, pipe geometry) and output quantities (e.g. velocity). Further details can be found in see, e.g. [2].

The model is trained on a dataset consisting of abundant CFD simulations and sparse LDV measurements, defined as pairs (x, y) , where x represents the input vector of physical and geometrical parameters and y is the output vector quantity of interest (e.g., the normalized axial velocity) represented on a polar grid of the pipe cross-section.

The Gaussian Process (GP) is defined as: $\hat{y}(x) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu(x), \sigma^2(x))$, where $\mu(x)$ is the mean function and $\sigma^2(x)$ is the observation variance, which is the sum of functional uncertainty from the kernel and heteroskedastic noise from high-fidelity and low-fidelity. The kernel defines the similarity and how information propagates in the parameter space [3]. Typical choices for the kernel include Radial Basis Function (RBF), Matérn or White Kernel. The hyperparameters (length-scale, process variance and noise variance) are estimated by maximizing the log marginal likelihood. For further details regarding GP and kernel modeling, see e.g. [4] and [5].

2.2. Model Improvement and Criteria for Refinement

Once the initial surrogate has been constructed, its capability is verified against pre-defined performance and reliability criteria. If the model does not meet these criteria, several improvement strategies, in general, can be applied:

1. Adaptive Sampling (Active Learning): New simulation or measurement points are added where the model's predictive variance is high or where the model shows large residuals [6].
2. Kernel refinement: Introduction of additional kernels that capture directional dependencies and physical correlations [7].
3. Uncertainty recalibration: Apply conformal calibration using a score function $S = \frac{|y - \mu(x)|}{\sigma(x)}$ to guarantee empirical coverage [8].
4. Model hierarchy: Combine multiple surrogate types (e.g., local GPs or polynomial chaos expansions) to improve local accuracy or handle nonlinear regimes [9] [10] [11].

2.3. Separation of Calibration and Validation Data

To ensure unbiased performance assessment, data must be separated into calibration (training) and validation (testing) subsets. Calibration data are used to train the surrogate, while validation data are reserved for assessing predictive performance and uncertainty calibration.

For small datasets, cross-validation (e.g., leave-one-out) is preferable. When data are from both CFD and experiments, CFD data are primarily used for training and experimental data for validation to assess generalization beyond numerical conditions.

2.4. Treatment of Error and Uncertainty Sources

In flow metering applications, several sources of error contribute to the overall uncertainty of VEs. In addition to others, the surrogate model itself contributes to them.

2.4.1. Background: Flow Meter Measurements

In realistic installations, flow conditions are often disturbed by upstream fittings, bends or junctions. These disturbances require fluid-mechanical calibration factors to adjust measured flow rates. As it is impractical to determine these factors experimentally for every possible configuration, CFD-based VEs are used to determine them computationally.

Figure 1: Workflow of a virtual flow meter in real world applications

A typical setup involves an ultrasonic flow meter installed downstream of a specific flow disturbance, see Figure 1. Using the measured mean path velocity and the reference flow rate, fluid mechanical calibration factors are determined for different operating conditions. However, since the determination of the reference flow rate is time consuming and costly due to the need for physical calibration setups, VEs compute appropriate fluid mechanical calibration factors by applying the ultrasonic measurement principle to CFD-derived flow fields. For more information about virtual flow meter approaches, see e.g. [12], [13], [14], [15], [16] and [17].

2.4.2. Errors and Uncertainties in the Virtual Representation of the Instrument

- Simplified implementation of the measuring principle
- Interpolation between CFD grid points
- Approximation errors of numerical integrals
- Simplified or idealized sensor geometry

2.4.3. Errors and Uncertainties in the Real Experiment

- Installation angle deviations
- Calibration errors of the reference meter
- Distance between the meter and the disturbance element
- Temperature and pressure fluctuations of the working fluid
- Uncertainty in reference flow rate representation
- Reproducibility and long-term stability of the flow meter
- Repeatability of measurements
- Geometrical tolerances (pipe diameter, bend radii, wall roughness)
- Signal processing effects (noise, drift, or electronic disturbance)

2.4.4. Errors and Uncertainties in the Virtual Representation of the Measurand

- Modeling errors due to approximations of the Navier–Stokes equations and turbulence model choices
- Numerical errors: discretization, convergence and round-off errors
- Surrogate model approximation error
- Input data quality (simulation and experimental data)

2.5. Surrogate Model Validation

In order to guarantee that the surrogate model is suitable for use in metrology applications, a thorough validation procedure was carried out. This procedure involved comparing the model's predictions with high-fidelity LDV measurements. The validation process involves a strict separation between training, calibration and validation data to ensure unbiased performance assessment.

2.5.1. Dataset Composition and Data Separation

The dataset under consideration includes 224 velocity field samples: 196 CFD simulations are used as low-fidelity training data and 28 LDV measurements are used as high-fidelity data for training, conformal calibration and validation. Each sample consists of a two-dimensional velocity field on a polar grid of 40 azimuthal and 30 radial positions for a double S-elbow pipe configuration with an inner pipe diameter of $D = 0.1$ m, see Figure 2. The input parameter variable is four-dimensional, see Table 1.

It is important to clarify the role of the LDV data: In a multi-fidelity framework, LDV measurements serve as high-fidelity data that is used for multiple purposes. A subset of LDV data is included in the training set to enable the model to learn the CFD to LDV correction (bias correction). Another subset is reserved for conformal calibration (to determine the scaling factor for uncertainty quantification) and the remaining subset is used for independent validation. This is fundamentally different from single-fidelity approaches where all experimental data would be treated identically. The key distinction is that in multi-fidelity modeling, the high-fidelity data informs the model about systematic differences between simulation and experiment, while the held-out validation data tests whether these corrections generalize to unseen conditions.

Figure 2: LDV measurement grid (left), double s-elbow pipe configuration (right)

Table 1: Design space of the surrogate model

Parameter	Description	Value Range
R_c/D [-]	Normalized curvature radius	[1.0, 1.425, 2.5]
w_{vol} [m/s]	Volumetric flow rate	[0.16, 0.40, 0.80, 2.00, 4.00, 5.60]
z/D [-]	Normalized downstream distance at test rig	[2.43, 5.56, 10.69, 12.43, 15.69, 22.56, 32.69]
d_l/D [-]	Normalized distance between two bends at test rig	[0.0, 0.93, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 6.06, 10.0, 20.0, 30.0, 40.0]

CFD data span multiple R_c/D configurations [1.0, 1.425, 2.5] at a single flow condition (id1), while LDV measurements were obtained for six flow conditions (id0-id5) for one R_c/D value and two d_l/D values ($0.93 \approx 1$ and $6.06 \approx 6$).

The data is systematically divided based on z/D positions and flow conditions: Training data comprises all 196 CFD simulations (covering all R_c/D configurations [1.0, 1.425, 2.5]) plus LDV measurements from flow conditions id0, id2, id3 and id5 at the downstream position $z/D = [12.43]$, as well as id1 at downstream positions $z/D = [5.56, 10.69, 12.43, 22.56, 32.69]$ and id4 at downstream positions $z/D = [2.43, 10.69, 12.43, 15.69, 32.69]$. Conformal calibration uses LDV measurements from id4 at $z/D = [5.56, 22.56]$. Independent validation uses LDV measurements from id1 at $z/D = [2.43, 15.69]$. This split ensures that the validation data represents one flow condition at two d_l/D , each at a downstream position close and another one distant to the disturbance. These parameter combinations are, for the chosen flow id, completely held out from the training and uncertainty calibration process, enabling an unbiased assessment of the model performance and uncertainty estimates. An overview of all flow conditions is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Overview of flow conditions of the surrogate model

id	$Re_{undisturbed}$ [-]	Flow rate Q [m ³ /h]	Volumetric flow rate w_{vol} [m/s]
0	2.0E+04	4.53	0.16
1	5.00E+04	11.32	0.40
2	1.00E+05	22.64	0.80
3	2.50E+05	56.6	2.00
4	5.00E+05	113.2	4.00
5	7.0E+05	158.48	5.60

2.5.2. Multi-Fidelity Model Architecture

The surrogate utilizes an Auto-Regressive Multi-Fidelity (AR-MF) GP framework with separate models for the symmetric and asymmetric velocity components. The axial velocity component w can be decomposed as follows:

$$w = w_{sym} + w_{asym},$$

where w_{sym} and w_{asym} represent the axisymmetric and asymmetric part of the flow profile, respectively. The entire velocity field is decomposed via Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), where the zero-frequency component (mode $m = 0$) corresponds to the azimuthal mean $a_0(r)$, which naturally serves as the symmetric base profile and reduces the symmetric component to a one-dimensional radial profile. Higher Fourier modes ($m > 0$) capture the asymmetric flow structures with full radial dependence. This decomposition simultaneously achieves computational efficiency leading to a data reduction of 72.5 %. Furthermore, the framework allows heteroskedastic noise modelling, which is an appropriate technique that accounts for the different fidelity levels: LDV measurements are assigned to α_{LDV} and CFD simulations to α_{CFD} , with $\alpha_{LDV} < \alpha_{CFD}$ reflecting higher confidence in experimental data. Regarding the validation, different noise variances were considered from expert information.

2.5.3. Uncertainty Quantification and Conformal Calibration

The GPR framework provides uncertainty estimates through the posterior variance. Conformal calibration is applied to ensure reliable coverage, yielding a calibration RMSE of 0.0153 and a conformal calibration factor of $k_{alpha} = 0.99$, which fell below the Gaussian reference of 1.96. A conservative floor of $k_{alpha} \geq 1.96$ is declared to ensure that prediction intervals are at least as wide as a classical Gaussian 95 % interval. This floor guards against GP overconfidence, which can occur when the posterior variance from multi-output GPs with limited training data is too narrow. Concluding, the native GPR uncertainty estimates already provide sufficient coverage without additional scaling. For a 95 % confidence level, this result demonstrates the benefit of conformal calibration for complex multi-fidelity models: rather than relying on potentially misspecified distributional assumptions, the data-driven calibration ensures that uncertainty estimates are reliable in practice.

2.5.4. Validation Results

A comprehensive bias analysis was performed on both the calibration and validation datasets to assess systematic deviations between the surrogate model predictions and the LDV reference measurements. The results are summarized as follows in Table 3:

Table 3: Bias analysis of calibration and validation dataset

	Calibration	Validation
Mean Bias [-]	-0.008363	-0.000461
Median Bias [-]	-0.008461	0.000136
RMSE [-]	0.0153	0.0156

Systematic deviations between surrogate model predictions and LDV reference measurements were quantified through bias analysis across all spatial points and measurement conditions. Mean bias represents the average difference between model predictions and actual measurements, where values close to zero indicate that the model does not systematically over- or underpredict the velocity. As a robust alternative, median bias provides the middle value of the residual distribution, being less sensitive to outliers. The per-sample RMSE captures the typical magnitude of prediction errors regardless of positive or negative sign and is obtained by first computing the RMSE for each individual measurement plane and then averaging over all planes, thus giving equal weight to each

flow condition. Notably, near-zero mean bias values (calibration: -0.0083, validation: -0.0005) demonstrate that the multi-fidelity framework successfully corrects for systematic CFD-LDV discrepancies. The per-sample validation RMSE (1.56 %) is comparable to the per-sample calibration RMSE (1.53 %), indicating that the model generalizes well to unseen measurement conditions and does not overfit to the calibration data.

Figure 4 presents a reduced set of four representative validation cases, selected to highlight the key physical phenomena and the surrogate model's predictive capabilities across different flow regimes. The selection criteria prioritize: (1) contrasting downstream positions (close to disturbance region vs. developed region) and (2) varying d_1/D distances ($d_1/D \approx 1$ close bends arrangement vs. $d_1/D \approx 6$ far bend arrangement). The polar contour plots display the normalized axial velocity distribution $w_{norm} = w/w_{vol}$ across the pipe cross-section, where the radial coordinate r/R extends from the pipe center ($r/R = 0$) to the wall ($r/R = 1$) and the azimuthal angle φ indicates the angular position. In the region close to the disturbance ($z/D \approx 2.43$), the flow shows asymmetry with higher velocities on the upper/inner pipe region (high-momentum region) and reduced velocities on the lower/outer pipe region. This pattern results from pressure-driven secondary flows induced by the upstream disturbances. For $d_1/D \approx 6$, the initial distortion is more pronounced, indicating that the secondary flows from the first bend have fully developed before entering the second bend, leading to superimposed flow structures. In contrast, for $d_1/D \approx 1$, the flow appears more uniform near the disturbance, as the short separation distance causes partial cancellation of opposing vortices. In the developed region ($z/D \approx 15.69$), the velocity profile for $d_1/D \approx 6$ approaches the fully developed flow distribution, though residual asymmetries persist due to incomplete dissipation of the secondary flow structures. Compared to $d_1/D \approx 1$, the asymmetry continues to develop further downstream, indicating a delayed flow redistribution due to the initially suppressed secondary flow structures.

The error plots (rightmost column) reveal that prediction errors are generally below ± 6 % of the local velocity in the developed region, with the largest deviations occurring in regions of rapid velocity gradients. Red markers in the prediction panels indicate points where the LDV measurements fall outside the 95 % confidence bounds, serving as a diagnostic for potential model deficiencies or measurement outliers. Outliers are observed primarily at $z/D = 2.43$ for $d_1/D \approx 6$, where the flow exhibits the strongest asymmetry and steepest velocity gradients. Here, the low outlier rate confirms that the uncertainty quantification is well-calibrated. Even in regions close to the disturbance, it is possible to capture the overall velocity distribution. The multi-fidelity framework successfully corrects any errors in the CFD data within the design space, but physical validation is recommended for extrapolation to untested configurations.

Figure 3: Validation examples showing (left to right): LDV reference measurement, surrogate model prediction with 95% confidence bounds (outliers marked in red) and prediction error (LDV - prediction).

The validation results demonstrate that the surrogate model meets requirements for use in virtual flow experiments, since the observed prediction accuracy (RMSE of 1.53 % for calibration and 1.56 % for validation) and uncertainty quantification to maintain accuracy are satisfied. Regarding the uncertainty quantification: with a 95% confidence interval, statistical theory predicts that approximately 5% of measurements will fall outside the uncertainty bounds even for a perfectly calibrated model. The red outlier markers in Figure 4 are therefore not indicative of model failure but rather serve as a diagnostic tool for identifying regions where additional investigation may be appropriate. The observed outlier rate is consistent with the expected 5% level, confirming that the uncertainty quantification through conformal calibration is well-calibrated. Points outside the 95%

confidence interval may arise from measurement uncertainty in the LDV data, localized flow phenomena not captured by the surrogate or regions of particularly high velocity gradients. The model successfully fuses CFD simulations with sparse LDV measurements, allowing predictions over the full parameter space while maintaining traceability to experimental reference data. Uncertainty quantification provides reliable confidence intervals that can be propagated through the virtual measurement chain.

3. A surrogate model of a welded part

3.1. The part

Welded steel structures are used widely in many applications. When welded structures are used in moving vehicles weight is minimized for practical and energy saving reasons. However, an engineering problem is how to minimize weight without compromising structural rigidity. In addition there are also unintentional variations in manufacturing.

The part is designed by VTT and manufactured with tolerances typical for welded structures used in train wagons (Figure 4). Because the intention was to get typical welding quality the company which manufactured the part did not know that VTT would be the end user. Therefore, manufacturing was not aware of future metrological and scientific use. The idea is to demonstrate the concept to use measured geometrical data for fatigue and life-time analysis. This would be a DT [18]. Under cyclic load there is a “flow of stress” through the structure and misalignments between plates are critical to fatigue. Roughly speaking misalignment larger than 10 % of plate thickness are starting to be critical. For a plate thickness of 5 mm this would be 0.5 mm. In quality inspection the uncertainty should be about 20 % to 30 % of a critical value or tolerance. Fringe projection instruments are expected to be able to reach this uncertainty but the topic is complex and research is needed before concept is mature for industrial use.

Figure 4: Case CS8 part made by welding.

3.2. Need of surrogate model

The goal is to perform a structural finite element (FE) analysis to make a life-time analysis of fatigue. In machine design the FE analysis is done using the design Computer-Aided Design (CAD) model but a new concept is to use geometric data of an individual piece containing geometrical variations from manufacturing. This would be a DT instance. There exists a stereolithography (STL) file based on measured data of the part which contain full geometrical model of the part (Figure 5). Unfortunately, this would be computationally expensive. In addition, according to the presented concept every piece is measured and FE analysis is done every piece separately. Therefore, simplified parametric models are considered as an alternative. They could be built on

following features:

- One feature to be extracted is translation type misalignment (Figure 5).
- Another feature is angular error as angle between welded plates
- A measured curved geometry of a surface nominally flat in the CAD model can be described as cylinder surface (Figure 7)

The parametric model will not be as rich in details as the STL model which will contribute to uncertainty. The parametric model can have the format of a CAD model but should not be confused with the design CAD which is without geometrical variations from manufacturing.

Figure 5: The measured part will contain geometrical deviations which could be described as “Free Form”

Figure 6: Translation type misalignment generates local stress.

Figure 7: Examples of cylinder surfaces.

3.3. Surrogate model

To demonstrate concept of surrogate model, a welded X-joint was selected (Figure 8). The X-joint is now based on four planes (Figure 9).

The X-weld to be inspected and the plane elements for FEM analysis

Figure 8: Selected X-joint.

Figure 9: Surrogate model of X-joint based on planes.

3.4. Errors in the surrogate model

The errors and uncertainties in the surrogate model consist of

- Systematic errors of measurement instrument
- Industrial Repeatability & Reproducibility for mock-up
- Conversion errors, measured data → CAD, STL polygon size
- Errors due to surrogate

The two last error categories are related to generation of the surrogate model. The first two error

categories represent errors which occur before generation of the surrogate model but will propagate into the surrogate model.

Systematic errors in 3D measurements can be evaluated by procedures described in the ISO 10360 standard series. Here calibrated artefacts with known shape (plane or freeform) and length artefacts (gauge block, step gauge, ball bar and ball plate) can be used. Sometimes the instrument manufacturer publishes information on these errors. However, this is not done for every optical measurement instrument, probably because the topic is complex and task specific. During the ViDiT project, systematic errors for a typical fringe projection instrument was evaluated at a stakeholder and the measurement uncertainty was evaluated to 0.04 mm ($k=2$) for a measurement volume of 1 m³.

When instrument is used in industry to measure workpieces environmental effects such as temperature of workpiece and temperature changes of the instrument will contribute to errors. These can at least partly be estimated by repeatability and reproducibility tests. Documentation how these can be done are given in a document “Measurement System Analysis [19]. During the ViDiT project, repeatability errors for a fringe projection instrument was evaluated at a stakeholder and it was in the range 0.03 mm ... 0.07 mm [20].

In the case described here a x-joint is approximated by planes. A typical case of plane fitting of four planes is shown in Figure 10. The residuals or errors in plane fitting are easy to retrieve as side product of the fitting. In addition, as the original geometrical data is 3D including form errors different assumptions used in plane fitting will result in different residuals.

In Figure 11 is seen an example of how form error is not accounted for in the surrogate model consisting of planes.

Figure 10: Plane fitting of four planes.

Form deviation compared to the closest IGES Planes

Figure 11: Example of form error outside surrogate model. Magnitude is about 0.8 mm.

Reference measurements of the welded part can be used for validation purposes on the surrogate model.

As a summary it can be concluded that errors in surrogate model comes from four sources below

- Systematic errors of measurement instrument
- Industrial Repeatability & Reproducibility
- File conversions
- Uncertainty from geometrical simplifications when generating simplified plane data for FE

The magnitude of the errors can be evaluated by comparing the 3D data of the surrogate model with scanned 3D data which is in the beginning of the described workflow.

4. A surrogate model for a 3D robotic DT

4.1. Surrogate model construction

The development of the surrogate model for the 3D robotic DT was based on a dimensionality reduction strategy. The full DT model (see Figure 12) included a wide set of geometric parameters such as Denavit-Hartenberg parameters and tool/base misalignment values, many of which are either non-observable or highly correlated [21] [22].

Figure 12: Robot parameters full kinematic parameters

A sensitivity analysis was conducted (see Figure a) using the Jacobian matrix of the calibration model, to determine which parameters had a significant effect on output uncertainty. Simultaneously, a correlation analysis was performed (see Figure b) to detect collinear parameter pairs (correlation close to ± 1) which hinder independent identification. These analyses led to the selection of a reduced set of relevant parameters [23].

Figure 13: Sensitivity and correlation of the robot parameters; a) Sensitivity analysis of the Denavit-Hartenberg Parameters, b) Correlation matrix of DT parameters

This reduced set became the basis of the surrogate model (see Figure 14), which preserved fidelity for uncertainty propagation but with significantly lower computational cost. It enabled an efficient calibration process without the need to estimate redundant or non-influential parameters.

Figure 14: Parameters selection for calibration surrogate model

4.2. Model improvement

In this it is discussed how to improve the model based on defined criteria, e.g., in case the model did not suffice these criteria.

Model improvement followed two main quantitative criteria:

1. **Sensitivity index:** Parameters with high sensitivity values (e.g., >3 for translations, >0.2 for angular parameters) were reviewed and removed when they introduced instability. (See Figure 15.)
2. **Correlation matrix:** Strongly correlated parameters ($|\text{corr}| \approx 1$) were excluded, as they could not be independently estimated. (See Figure 16.)

Alternative configurations of the calibration test were also explored to ensure better excitation of the remaining parameters. For instance, changing the spatial configuration of the measurement targets led to improved parameter observability.

These refinements ensured that the surrogate model retained its ability to reflect real system behavior while reducing unnecessary complexity.

Figure 15: Sensitivity analysis for the optimum parameter identification

Figure 16: Correlation matrix for the optimum parameters identification

4.3. Separation of calibration and validation data

The validation of the surrogate model required a clear separation between calibration and validation datasets:

Calibration was performed using a reference artifact (a 4-sphere target) measured by a coordinate measuring machine (CMM), which served to calibrate the DT parameters.

Validation involved a second test using a different part with geometric and freeform features, also measured by CMM and TripleScan. The purpose was to evaluate the accuracy of the DT when applied to complex surfaces not used during calibration.

Results were obtained for both the full and surrogate models (see Figure 17). By comparing the uncertainty estimation results, it was possible to validate that the surrogate model maintained acceptable error levels while offering a reduction in computational cost.

(a)

(b)

Figure 17: Validated on a geometric and freeform part measurement uncertainty; a) Using full model, b) Using surrogate model (bottom).

4.4. Treatment of Different Error Sources

Several sources of error were identified and treated in the model:

- Measurement error from the CMM and Laser Tracker was modeled using Gaussian distributions, particularly in the Monte Carlo simulation stage.
- Model error due to the inclusion of non-observable or highly correlated parameters was minimized through model reduction.
- Numerical error related to the uncertainty propagation via Monte Carlo (MC) was studied by analyzing the effect of the number of MC cycles.

A systematic experiment was performed to assess the influence of the number of Monte Carlo cycles on the stability of uncertainty results (see Figure 18). It was observed that:

- The uncertainty values stabilized after ~20,000 MC cycles.
- The difference in uncertainty between successive cycle counts dropped below 0.01 mm after 40,000 cycles.
- The computation time scaled linearly with the number of cycles (approx. 0.0173 s per cycle), which justifies the need for surrogate model efficiency.

Figure 18: Evolution of uncertainty and computation time as a function of Monte Carlo cycles

References

- [1] N. Bayazit, M. Straka, K. Oberleithner and S. Schmelter, "Uncertainty-Aware 2D Flow Prediction Using Multi-Fidelity Surrogate Modeling in Virtual Flow Metering," in *The 20th International Flow Measurement Conference (FLOMEKO 2026)*, Nara, Japan, 2026.
- [2] N. Baillie, B. Kerleguer, C. Feau and J. Garnier, *Efficient multi-fidelity Gaussian process regression for noisy outputs and non-nested experimental designs*, arXiv, 2025.
- [3] S. Pu, "Optimizing Gaussian processes: Powerful kernels and efficiency improvements," in *2024 2ND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPUTER SCIENCE AND MECHATRONICS (ICCSM 2024)*, 2024.
- [4] D. Duvenaud, "Automatic model construction with Gaussian processes," Apollo - University of Cambridge Repository, 2014.
- [5] C. E. Rasmussen and C. K. I. Williams, *Gaussian processes for machine learning*, 3. print ed., Cambridge, Mass. [u.a.]: MIT Press, 2008.
- [6] A. Tristani and C. Arson, *Active learning with physics-informed neural networks for optimal sensor placement in deep tunneling through transversely isotropic elastic rocks*, arXiv, 2025.
- [7] K. Chen, T. van Laarhoven, J. Chen and E. Marchiori, "Incorporating Dependencies in Spectral Kernels for Gaussian Processes," in *Machine Learning and Knowledge Discovery in Databases*, Springer International Publishing, 2020, p. 565–581.
- [8] J. Y. Araz and M. Spannowsky, *Another Fit Bites the Dust: Conformal Prediction as a Calibration Standard for Machine Learning in High-Energy Physics*, arXiv, 2025.
- [9] D. Busby, "Hierarchical adaptive experimental design for Gaussian process emulators," *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, vol. 94, p. 1183–1193, July 2009.
- [10] I.-G. Farçaş, B. Peherstorfer, T. Neckel, F. Jenko and H.-J. Bungartz, "Context-aware learning of hierarchies of low-fidelity models for multi-fidelity uncertainty quantification," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 406, p. 115908, March 2023.
- [11] K. Ravi, V. Fediukov, F. Dietrich, T. Neckel, F. Buse, M. Bergmann and H.-J. Bungartz, "Multi-fidelity Gaussian process surrogate modeling for regression problems in physics," *Machine Learning: Science and Technology*, vol. 5, p. 045015, October 2024.
- [12] N. Bayazit, M. Marschall, M. Straka and S. Schmelter, "A novel framework for the uncertainty evaluation of virtual flow meters," *Measurement Science and Technology*, vol. 36, p. 076012, July 2025.
- [13] A. Weissenbrunner, A. Fiebach, M. Juling and P. U. Thamsen, "A COUPLED NUMERICAL AND LASER OPTICAL METHOD FOR ON-SITE CALIBRATION OF FLOW METERS," in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Uncertainty Quantification in Computational Sciences and Engineering (UNCECOMP 2017)*, 2017.
- [14] A. Weissenbrunner, A. Ekatt, M. Straka and S. Schmelter, "A virtual flow meter downstream of various elbow configurations," *Metrologia*, vol. 60, p. 054002, August 2023.
- [15] A. Weissenbrunner, A. Fiebach, S. Schmelter, M. Bär, P. U. Thamsen and T. Lederer, "Simulation-based determination of systematic errors of flow meters due to uncertain inflow conditions," *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, vol. 52, p. 25–39, December 2016.
- [16] M. Straka, A. Weissenbrunner, C. Koglin, C. Höhne and S. Schmelter, "Simulation Uncertainty for a Virtual Ultrasonic Flow Meter," *Metrology*, vol. 2, p. 335–359, July 2022.
- [17] S. Schmelter, A. Fiebach, R. Model and M. Bär, "Numerical prediction of the influence of

- uncertain inflow conditions in pipes by polynomial chaos," *International Journal of Computational Fluid Dynamics*, vol. 29, p. 411–422, July 2015.
- [18] B. Schleich, N. Anwer, L. Mathieu and S. Wartzack, "Shaping the digital twin for design and production engineering," *CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 66, 2017.
- [19] ASTM International, "ASTM E2782-17, Standard Guide for Measurement Systems Analysis (MSA), DOI 10.1520/E2782-17R22E01.," ASTM, 2022.
- [20] J. Marttila, "3d-mittausjärjestelmän tilastollinen analyysi," Bachelor thesis at Savonia University of Applied Sciences, Kuopio, 2024.
- [21] A. Şirinterlikçi, M. Tiryakioğlu, A. Bird, A. Harris and K. Kweder, "Repeatability and Accuracy of an Industrial Robot: Laboratory Experience for a Design of Experiments Course 2009," *Technol Interface Journal/Spring*, 2009.
- [22] T. Motta JMS, "Robot Calibration: Modeling Measurement and Applications," *Industrial Robotics: Programming, Simulation and Applications. Pro Literatur Verlag, Germany / ARS, Austria*, 2006.
- [23] M. Vincze, S. Spiess, M. Parotidis and M. Götz, "Automatic generation of non-redundant and complete models for geometric and non-geometric errors of robots," *Int J Model Simul*. 1999;19(3):236-243.